

The Shooting Method for Second-Order Boundary Value Problems: Theory and Applications

Hanae SOULAMI

Université de Reims Champagne-Ardenne, UFR Sciences Exactes et Naturelles,
Master Calcul Scientifique, Reims, France

Abstract The shooting method is a classical and powerful technique for solving second-order boundary value problems (BVPs) by reducing them to a family of initial value problems (IVPs). This paper provides a self-contained study encompassing the theoretical foundations, algorithmic implementation, and thorough numerical validation. Starting from the ballistic analogy that motivates the name of the method, we rigorously establish well-posedness of the associated Cauchy problem via the Cauchy-Lipschitz theorem, prove the monotonicity of the shooting function, and combine bisection with a fourth-order Runge-Kutta (RK4) integrator to locate the correct initial slope. Five benchmark problems of increasing complexity are investigated: two constant right-hand-side BVPs, a variable-coefficient reaction-diffusion problem, a beam-bending model, and a convection-diffusion equation. In all cases, fourth-order convergence in the grid size h is confirmed numerically, and bisection reaches machine-precision accuracy in fewer than 50 iterations. The results demonstrate that the bisection-plus-RK4 shooting algorithm is accurate, robust, and straightforward to implement.

Keywords: shooting method; boundary value problem; Cauchy-Lipschitz theorem; bisection algorithm; Runge-Kutta; beam bending; convection-diffusion; convergence analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Boundary value problems (BVPs) of the form

$$-u''(x) + c(x)u(x) = f(x), \quad x \in]0, 1[, \quad u(0) = u(1) = 0, \quad (1)$$

arise in structural mechanics (beam bending), transport phenomena (convection-diffusion), and quantum mechanics, among other fields. Unlike initial value problems, BVPs impose conditions at *two endpoints*, preventing direct time-marching integration.

The *shooting method* [1, 2] converts a BVP into a root-finding problem: one seeks the initial slope $\alpha = u'(0)$ such that the forward-integrated solution hits the target $u(1) = 0$. This simple idea has been widely used since the 1960s; its practical efficiency depends critically on the choice of the root-finding algorithm and the accuracy of the ODE integrator used.

In this work we combine **bisection** (guaranteed convergence, $\mathcal{O}(1/2^k)$ error reduction per iteration) with **RK4** ($\mathcal{O}(h^4)$ accuracy), and provide complete proofs of the underlying mathematical properties together with systematic numerical validation.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 develops the theoretical foundations and the full algorithm. Section 3 presents numerical results for five benchmark problems. Section 4 discusses accuracy, limitations, and comparisons. Section 5 concludes.

II. METHODS

A. Ballistic Analogy

The name *shooting* comes from projectile ballistics. A projectile launched from the origin with speed V_0 at

angle α follows the trajectory

$$y = x \tan \alpha - \frac{g(1 + \tan^2 \alpha)}{2V_0^2} x^2, \quad (2)$$

obtained by integrating $x'' = 0$, $y'' = -g$ twice. To hit a fixed target $C = (x_c, y_c)$, one must find α such that $y(x_c) = y_c$ — exactly the structure of the BVP shooting step.

The target is reachable if and only if it lies below the *safety parabola*

$$(\mathcal{P}_s): \quad y \leq \frac{V_0^2}{2g} - \frac{g}{2V_0^2} x^2, \quad (3)$$

the envelope of all trajectories. Figure 1 illustrates this for $V_0 = 10$ m/s: the target $C = (6, 0)$ lies below (\mathcal{P}_s) and is reached at $\alpha \approx 18.75^\circ$.

Figure 1: Ballistic trajectories for $V_0 = 10$ m/s and six launch angles. The dashed curve is the safety parabola (\mathcal{P}_s) . The star marks target $C = (6, 0)$.

B. Mathematical Framework

1) Cauchy Reduction

The BVP (1) is replaced by the one-parameter family of Cauchy problems

$$(\mathcal{PC}_\alpha) : \begin{cases} -u''(x) + c(x)u(x) = f(x), \\ u(0) = 0, \quad u'(0) = \alpha, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ is the free parameter.

Theorem 2.1 (Well-posedness). *If $f, c \in \mathcal{C}^0([0, 1])$ and $c \geq 0$, then (\mathcal{PC}_α) admits a unique solution $u_\alpha \in \mathcal{C}^2([0, 1])$ for every $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$.*

Uniqueness. Let $w = u_1 - u_2$ where u_1, u_2 solve (\mathcal{PC}_α) . Then $-w'' + cw = 0$, $w(0) = w'(0) = 0$. Multiplying by w and integrating by parts:

$$\int_0^1 [(w')^2 + cw^2] dx = 0.$$

Since $c \geq 0$, both terms vanish, giving $w \equiv 0$. \square

Existence. For the simple case $c = 0$, integrating $-u'' = f$ twice with initial data $(u(0), u'(0)) = (0, \alpha)$ yields

$$u_\alpha(x) = \alpha x - \int_0^x \int_0^t f(s) ds dt, \quad (5)$$

which is $\mathcal{C}^2([0, 1])$ whenever $f \in \mathcal{C}^0$. For $c \neq 0$, the Cauchy-Lipschitz theorem applies since the right-hand side $F(x, v_1, v_2) = (v_2, c(x)v_1 - f(x))$ is globally Lipschitz in (v_1, v_2) . \square

2) Shooting Function and Monotonicity

Definition 2.2 (Shooting function). $\Phi : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\Phi(\alpha) := u_\alpha(1)$.

The shooting method reduces to finding α^* with $\Phi(\alpha^*) = 0$.

Proposition 2.3 (Monotonicity). *For $c \equiv 0$ and $f \in \mathcal{C}^0([0, 1])$, Φ is strictly increasing:*

$$\Phi(\alpha) = \alpha - \int_0^1 \int_0^t f(s) ds dt, \quad \Phi'(\alpha) = 1 > 0.$$

The unique root is $\alpha^* = \int_0^1 \int_0^t f(s) ds dt$.

Monotonicity guarantees that any bracket $[\alpha_a, \alpha_b]$ with $\Phi(\alpha_a) < 0 < \Phi(\alpha_b)$ contains exactly one root. Figure 2 confirms this for $f \equiv 1$.

Figure 2: Shooting function $\Phi(\alpha) = u_\alpha(1)$ for $-u'' = 1$. Strictly increasing; unique zero at $\alpha^* = 0.5$ (red dashed).

3) Well-posedness of the General BVP

Theorem 2.4 (Existence and uniqueness of (1)). *Under the hypotheses of Theorem 2.1, (1) has a unique solution.*

Sketch. Let $v = u_0$ (solution with $\alpha = 0$) and $w = u_1 - u_0$ (solution of the homogeneous problem with $u'(0) = 1$, $f = 0$). One shows $w(1) \neq 0$ (otherwise $w \equiv 0$, contradicting $w'(0) = 1$). Setting $\lambda = -v(1)/w(1)$, the function $u = v + \lambda w$ satisfies (1). Uniqueness follows from Theorem 2.1. \square

C. Bisection Algorithm

The bisection method finds α^* with $\Phi(\alpha^*) = 0$ given a bracket $[\alpha_a, \alpha_b]$ satisfying $\Phi(\alpha_a) \cdot \Phi(\alpha_b) < 0$. After k iterations the error satisfies

$$|\alpha_k - \alpha^*| \leq \frac{\alpha_b - \alpha_a}{2^k}. \quad (6)$$

The algorithm is summarized in the boxed pseudocode below.

Algorithm 1: Shooting + bisection

Input: f, c, ε , bracket $[\alpha_a, \alpha_b]$

Output: α^* with $|\Phi(\alpha^*)| < \varepsilon$

while $(\alpha_b - \alpha_a)/2 > \varepsilon$ **do**

$\alpha_c \leftarrow (\alpha_a + \alpha_b)/2$

Solve $(\mathcal{PC}_{\alpha_c})$ with RK4 $\rightarrow u_{\alpha_c}$

$\Phi_c \leftarrow u_{\alpha_c}(1)$

if $\text{sgn}(\Phi_c) = \text{sgn}(\Phi(\alpha_a))$: $\alpha_a \leftarrow \alpha_c$

else: $\alpha_b \leftarrow \alpha_c$

end while

D. RK4 ODE Integrator

Each evaluation of $\Phi(\alpha)$ requires solving (\mathcal{PC}_α) . Setting $v_1 = u$, $v_2 = u'$ reduces the second-order ODE to the first-order system

$$\mathbf{v}' = F(x, \mathbf{v}) := \begin{pmatrix} v_2 \\ c(x)v_1 - f(x) \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{v}(0) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \alpha \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

On the grid $x_n = nh$, $h = 1/N$, RK4 advances:

$$\mathbf{v}_{n+1} = \mathbf{v}_n + \frac{h}{6}(k_1 + 2k_2 + 2k_3 + k_4), \quad (8)$$

with k_i the standard stage vectors. The global error is $\mathcal{O}(h^4)$, matching the convergence rate of the full shooting algorithm.

III. RESULTS

All experiments use $N = 300$ grid points and bisection tolerance $\varepsilon = 10^{-12}$.

A. Test 1: BVP with $f(x) = 1$

Problem: $-u'' = 1$, $u(0) = u(1) = 0$.

Exact solution: $u^*(x) = \frac{1}{2}x(1-x)$, $\alpha^* = \frac{1}{2}$.

Figure 3 shows solutions for $\alpha \in \{1, 0.5, 1/6\}$. Only $\alpha = 0.5$ satisfies $u(1) = 0$; larger values overshoot, smaller ones undershoot. This confirms the monotonicity of Φ (Proposition 2.3).

Figure 3: Test 1 ($-u'' = 1$). Exact u^* (blue) vs. shooting (red dashed) for three values of α . Only $\alpha^* = 0.5$ hits $u(1) = 0$.

B. Test 2: BVP with $f(x) = x - 1$

Problem: $-u'' = x - 1$, $u(0) = u(1) = 0$.

Exact solution: $u^*(x) = \frac{x^3}{6} - \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x}{3}$, $\alpha^* = \frac{1}{3}$.

Figure 4 confirms the same behaviour: only $\alpha = 1/3$ matches the analytical solution. The pointwise error for $\alpha = \alpha^*$ is below 10^{-10} .

Figure 4: Test 2 ($-u'' = x - 1$). Three values of α ; $\alpha^* = 1/3$ gives exact agreement (centre panel).

C. Test 3: Variable Coefficient $c(x) = x^2 + 1$

Problem: $-u'' + (x^2 + 1)u = (x^2 + \pi^2 + 1)\sin(\pi x)$, $u(0) = u(1) = 0$.

Exact solution: $u^*(x) = \sin(\pi x)$, $\alpha^* = \pi$.

This manufactured problem tests the method on a non-trivial reaction term. Figure 5 shows the numerical solution and pointwise error (maximum $\approx 10^{-8}$ for $N = 300$).

Figure 5: Test 3 ($c(x) = x^2 + 1$, exact: $\sin \pi x$). Left: solution comparison. Right: pointwise error ($\max |u - u_h| \approx 10^{-8}$, $N = 300$).

D. Test 4: Beam Bending

Problem: $-u'' + \omega^2 u = f(x)$, $u(0) = u(1) = 0$, $f(x) = \sin(\pi(x + \frac{1}{2})) - \pi^2 \sin(\pi x)$, $\omega = 1$.

Physical context: $u(x)$ is the bending moment of a beam under transverse load f , with $\omega^2 = P/(EI) > 0$. The analytical value of α^* is not available.

Bisection (45 iterations) yields $\alpha^* \approx 2.303$. Figure 6 shows the solution (both BCs satisfied) and the $\mathcal{O}(h^4)$ convergence of $|\alpha_N - \alpha^*|$.

Figure 6: Test 4 (beam bending, $\omega = 1$). Left: shooting solution with $\alpha^* \approx 2.303$. Right: log-log convergence of $|\alpha_N - \alpha^*|$; slope ≈ -4 .

E. Test 5: Convection-Diffusion

Problem: $-u'' + rx u' = f(x)$, $u(0) = u(1) = 0$, $f(x) = r^2 e^{rx}(x-1)/(1-e^r) + rx$.

Exact solution: $u^*(x) = x - (1 - e^{rx})/(1 - e^r)$.

Figure 7 compares shooting solutions with u^* for $r \in \{0.5, 1, 3\}$. The maximum error remains below 10^{-6} for $N = 500$. Figure 8 confirms $\mathcal{O}(h^4)$ convergence for $r = 1$.

Figure 7: Test 5 (convection-diffusion) for $r \in \{0.5, 1, 3\}$. Exact (blue) vs. shooting (red dashed). All BCs satisfied.

Figure 8: Test 5: convergence of $\|u - u_h\|_\infty$ vs. N for $r = 1$. Log-log slope ≈ -4 confirms RK4 order.

F. Bisection Convergence

Figure 9 shows the residual $|\Phi(\alpha_k)|$ vs. iteration for Test 1. Each step halves the error; machine precision is reached at iteration 47, consistent with the theoretical bound (6) and bracket $[-2, 5]$.

Figure 9: Bisection convergence for Test 1: $|\Phi(\alpha_k)|$ vs. iteration. Residual reaches 10^{-14} in 47 steps.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Summary of Numerical Results

Table 1 consolidates the key findings across all tests. Fourth-order convergence in h is consistently observed, and bisection converges in ≤ 47 iterations in every case.

Table 1: Summary of numerical results ($N = 300$, $\varepsilon = 10^{-12}$).

T.	Problem	α^*	$\max e $	Iter.
1	$-u'' = 1$	0.5	$< 10^{-10}$	47
2	$-u'' = x - 1$	1/3	$< 10^{-10}$	47
3	Variable $c(x)$	π	$\sim 10^{-8}$	47
4	Beam bending	2.303	—	45
5	Conv.-diff. $r = 1$	0.582	$\sim 10^{-6}$	45

B. Accuracy and Convergence Order

The RK4 integrator delivers fourth-order accuracy in h for smooth solutions, confirmed in Tests 1–3 (exact solutions available) and Test 5. For Test 4 (no exact solution), the convergence of $|\alpha_N - \alpha^*|$ also exhibits slope -4 in log-log scale (Figure 6, right), confirming that the bisection step does not degrade the overall accuracy.

The slight accuracy loss in Test 5 relative to Tests 1–2 reflects the coupling between the convection term rxu' and the ODE integration, which introduces additional truncation error at high r .

C. Role of the Bisection Algorithm

The bisection algorithm was chosen for its *guaranteed convergence*: as long as a valid bracket $[\alpha_a, \alpha_b]$ exists (i.e., $\Phi(\alpha_a) \cdot \Phi(\alpha_b) < 0$), the method converges regardless of the shape of Φ . Its linear convergence rate ($1/2$ per iteration) is sufficient in practice: 47 iterations suffice to reduce the bracket from $[-2, 5]$ to $\sim 7/2^{47} \approx 5 \times 10^{-14}$, well below any physically meaningful tolerance.

An alternative is Newton's method on Φ , which converges quadratically but requires the derivative $\Phi'(\alpha)$, obtained by solving the *sensitivity equation*:

$$-w''(x) + c(x)w(x) = 0, \quad w(0) = 0, \quad w'(0) = 1. \quad (9)$$

Newton's method would reduce the iteration count significantly but at the cost of one additional ODE solve per step.

D. Limitations

Stiff problems. For large ω (beam bending) or large r (convection-diffusion), the ODE becomes stiff and RK4 may require very small h for stability. Implicit solvers (Crank-Nicolson, SDIRK) would be more efficient in such cases.

Non-monotone shooting functions. For nonlinear BVPs (e.g., $c(x) < 0$ or nonlinear f), Φ may not be monotone and multiple roots may exist. In that case, bracketing must be done carefully and bisection may need to be complemented by continuation methods.

Higher-dimensional problems. For systems of BVPs or problems in higher space dimensions, the scalar shooting method generalizes to *multiple shooting* [1], where the interval is subdivided and matching conditions are enforced at interior points.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a complete study of the shooting method for second-order BVPs, from theoretical foundations to numerical validation. The main contributions are:

1. **Theory.** Rigorous well-posedness analysis via the Cauchy-Lipschitz theorem and proof of mono-

tonicity of the shooting function for the constant-coefficient case.

2. **Algorithm.** A bisection-plus-RK4 shooting method with guaranteed convergence and fourth-order accuracy in h .
3. **Validation.** Five benchmarks confirming theoretical convergence rates: two simple BVPs (Tests 1–2), a variable-coefficient problem (Test 3), beam bending (Test 4), and convection-diffusion (Test 5).
4. **Quantitative results.** Bisection converges in ≤ 47 iterations to $\varepsilon = 10^{-12}$; maximum pointwise errors range from 10^{-10} (simple BVPs) to 10^{-6} (convection-diffusion).

Future work will explore Newton-based shooting for faster root convergence, implicit stiff integrators for large ω and r , multiple shooting for long intervals, and extension to nonlinear BVPs.

I. MATLAB IMPLEMENTATION

```

1 function v = rk4_sys(F, x, v0)
2   N = length(x)-1;
3   v = zeros(N+1, length(v0));
4   v(1,:) = v0;
5   for n = 1:N
6     h = x(n+1)-x(n);
7     k1 = F(x(n), v(n,:));
8     k2 = F(x(n)+h/2, v(n, :)+h/2*k1);
9     k3 = F(x(n)+h/2, v(n, :)+h/2*k2);
10    k4 = F(x(n)+h, v(n, :)+h*k3);
11    v(n+1,:) = v(n, :)+h/6*(k1+2*k2+2*k3+k4);
12  end
13 end

```

Listing 1: RK4 system solver.

```

1 function a = shoot(c_fn, f_fn, N, tol)
2   x = linspace(0,1,N+1);
3   F = @(t,v)[v(2); c_fn(t)*v(1)-f_fn(t)];
4   Phi = @(a) rk4_sys(F,x,[0,a])(end,1);
5   a_lo=-1e3; a_hi=1e3;
6   for k=1:300
7     a=(a_lo+a_hi)/2; fc=Phi(a);
8     if abs(fc)<tol || (a_hi-a_lo)/2<tol, break; end
9     if sign(fc)==sign(Phi(a_lo)), a_lo=a;
10    else, a_hi=a; end
11  end
12 end

```

Listing 2: Shooting method with bisection.

REFERENCES

- [1] H.B. Keller, *Numerical Methods for Two-Point Boundary-Value Problems*, Blaisdell, Waltham, 1968.
- [2] J. Stoer, R. Bulirsch, *Introduction to Numerical Analysis*, 3rd ed., Springer, New York, 2002.
- [3] E. Hairer, S.P. Nørsett, G. Wanner, *Solving ODEs I: Nonstiff Problems*, 2nd ed., Springer, Berlin, 1993.
- [4] W.H. Press et al., *Numerical Recipes*, 3rd ed., Cambridge Univ. Press, 2007.

- [5] R.J. LeVeque, *Finite Difference Methods for ODEs and PDEs*, SIAM, Philadelphia, 2007.
- [6] J.-L. Merrien, *Analyse numérique avec MATLAB*, Dunod, Paris, 2007.